

FATIGUE PROPERTIES OF QUASI-ISOTROPIC CARBON/EPOXY LAMINATES WITH PARTICLE DISPERSED INTERLAYERS

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ABSTRACT

This study deals with the effect of particle dispersed interlayers on the fatigue strength of quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates. Two kinds of the laminates with and without the particle dispersed interlayers (T800H/#3900 and T800H/#3631 laminates) were adopted here. Tension, compression and fully reversed (tension-compression) fatigue tests were performed for these laminates. The particle dispersed interlayers affected greatly the tension fatigue strength, and the tension fatigue strength was remarkably improved by introducing the particle dispersed layers. The particle dispersed interlayers suppressed the progressive interlaminar delamination from the free edge. In addition, the compressive and the fully reversed fatigue strengths were also improved by the existence of the particle dispersed layers.

INTRODUCTION

Quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates have been often used as a structural material in various applications. The various types of the fracture occur during loading in the quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates. Some of these are resin transverse cracks, splitting, delamination, shear fracture, and so on [1,2]. In particular, the progressive delamination often occurs from the free-edge under various loading conditions, and this reduces greatly the mechanical properties of the laminates. From such a viewpoint, many studies have been done for the improvement of delamination resistance, and various attempts have been proposed for this purpose; toughening of matrix [3], stitching[4,5], edge cap reinforcement [6,7], notched edges [8], discrete critical ply [9], interleaving [10-14], etc. Among them, the interleaving is a very simple technique to manufacture the laminate, and it gives high interlaminar toughness to the laminate. Recently the incorporating the plastic particle instead of the adhesive film between laminae has been attempted to improve the interlaminar toughness (see Fig.1), and it has been reported that the existence of the particle in the matrix phase is effective to improve some mechanical properties of carbon/epoxy laminate.

Carbon/epoxy laminates with plastic particle dispersed interlayers were prepared for the present work, and the effect of particle dispersion in the matrix phase of the interlayer on the fatigue properties of quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates is discussed.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

Materials used were two kinds of unidirectional carbon/epoxy prepregs; T800H/#3631 and T800H/#3900 (Toray Industries, Inc., Japan). T800H/#3900 prepreg was developed by adding

Figure 1. Laminates with and without particle dispersed interlayers.

the plastic particle dispersed interlayer to T800H/#3631 prepreg. Using these prepreps three kinds of quasi-isotropic laminates with different stacking sequences ($[0/\pm 45/90]_S$, $[0/+45/-45/90]_S$ and $[\pm 45/0/90]_S$) were prepared. All the laminates were fabricated by a vacuum bagging/autoclave curing technique. Geometries of the tension fatigue test specimen and the compression and fully reversed (tension-compression) fatigue test specimen are illustrated in Fig.2.

Tension fatigue, compression fatigue and fully reversed fatigue tests were performed by an electro-hydraulic fatigue testing machine (L7-2.50-S, Mori Engineering Co., Ltd., Japan) at the constant frequency of 10Hz under room temperature. Cyclic stress ratio, R , representing a ratio of minimum stress to maximum stress was fixed to 0.1, -1 and 10 for tension fatigue, compression fatigue and fully reversed fatigue, respectively. During the tension fatigue test, the fracture progress was observed by CCD scope in order to investigate the effect of particle dispersed interlayer on the fracture progress.

Figure 2. Geometries of tension fatigue and compression and fully reversed fatigue test specimens.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

EFFECT OF PARTICLE DISPERSED INTERLAYER ON FATIGUE STRENGTH

Fig.3 shows the relation between the cyclic tensile maximum stress and the number of fatigue cycles to failure. The tension fatigue strength of T800H/#3900 laminate was extremely higher than that of T800H/#3631 laminate. Both T800H/#3900 and T800H/#3631 laminates comprise

the same fiber/resin system and only different between two laminates is the existence of particle dispersed interlayers. Therefore the difference in the fatigue strength between T800H/#3900 and T800H/#3631 laminates is apparently caused by the effect of the particle dispersed interlayers. In T800H/#3631 laminate, the interlaminar delamination occurred from the free edges between -45° and 90° layers, and it progressed towards the center of the laminate. In addition, a little splitting failure occurred in 0° layers. The final failure was mainly caused by the delamination in T800H/#3631 laminate. In T800H/#3900 laminate, the interlaminar delamination occurred as same as that in T800H/#3631 laminate. However, the delamination occurred at higher stress level than that in T800H/#3631 laminate and it progressed more slowly. From these facts, it is obvious that the particle dispersion between layers can suppress the delamination progress between layers. In T800H/#3900 laminate the significant splitting failure occurred in 0° layer during fatigue loading. The final failure was mainly caused by the splitting failure in 0° layer in T800H/#3900 laminate. Such difference in the cause of the final failure is supposed to be induced by the difference in the delamination resistance due to the existence of the particle dispersed layers.

Fig.4 shows the relation between the cyclic maximum compressive stress and the number of fatigue cycles to failure. The compressive fatigue strength of T800H/#3900 laminate was also higher than that of T800H/#3631 laminate. At higher stress level, the fatigue strength of T800H/#3900 laminate was much higher than that of T800H/#3631 laminate, however, the difference is not large at low stress level. The effect of the incorporation of the particle dispersed layer was not remarkable compared with that in the tension fatigue test. On the fracture surface of T800H/#3900 laminate, many fiber breakages could be observed. On the other hand, such appearances could not be observed in T800H/#3631 laminate, and the pull-out of the fibers mainly

Figure 3. Relation between the maximum stress and the number of fatigue cycles to failure in tension fatigue test.

Figure 4. Relation between the compressive maximum stress and the number of fatigue cycles to failure in compression fatigue test.

Figure 5. Relation between the maximum stress and the number of fatigue cycles to failure in fully reversed fatigue test.

appeared. Microscopic failure was quite different between them. Such microscopic failure affects greatly the compressive fatigue strength.

Fig.5 shows the relation between the cyclic maximum stress and the number of fatigue cycles to failure in the fully reversed fatigue test. Fatigue strength of T800H/#3900 laminate was a little higher than that of T800H/#3631 laminate, however, the effect of the incorporation of the particle dispersed layer was less than that in the tension and compression fatigue tests. The main fracture in the fully reversed fatigue test was almost the same with that in the compression fatigue test since the compressive strength was much smaller than the tensile strength.

Figs.6 and 7 show the master diagrams at the number of fatigue cycles of 10^4 , 10^5 and 10^6 for T800H/#3900 and T800H/#3631 laminates, respectively. The static compressive strength was much smaller than the static tensile strength for both T800H/#3900 and T800H/#3631 laminates. The peak in the master diagram appeared where the mean stress was the tensile stress. This phenomenon is probably brought by the low compressive fatigue strength in comparison with tensile strength associated with the material investigated. The mean stress at the peak in the master diagram of T800H/#3900 laminate was higher than that of T800H/#3631 laminate. On the other hand, the difference in the master diagrams between T800H/#3900 and T800H/#3631 laminates was a little when the mean stress was 0 or minus value. This reflects that the tension fatigue strength of T800H/#3900 laminate was higher than that of T800H/#3631 laminate.

Figure 6. Master diagram for T800H/#3900 laminate.

Figure 7. Master diagram for T800H/#3631 laminate.

EFFECT OF STACKING SEQUENCE ON FATIGUE RESISTANCE

Figs.8 and 9 show the effect of stacking sequence on the fatigue strength under repeated tension loading for T800H/#3900 and T800H/#3631 laminates, respectively. In T800H/#3631 laminate, the tension fatigue strengths were different due to the stacking sequence. The fatigue strength of $[\pm 45/0/90]_S$ laminate was much higher than those of the other laminates. On the other hand, in T800H/#3900 laminate the tension fatigue strength was little affected by the stacking sequence. It is considered that the difference in the dependence of the fatigue strength on the stacking sequence between T800H/#3631 and T800H/#3900 laminates is closely related to the fracture process during fatigue loading. In T800H/#3631 laminate, the interlaminar delamination occurred at low stress and at a few fatigue cycles for all the laminates. In addition, the splitting failure in 0° layer occurred in $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ and $[0/+45/90/-45]_S$ laminates. In $[\pm 45/0/90]_S$ laminate the delamination originated between 0° and 90° layers from the free-edges, and it progressed rapidly with increasing the number of fatigue cycles. However, the damage in 90° layer did not progress to the other layers, and the splitting failure did not occur because 0° layer was placed at the inner layer. The progressive delamination occurred between -45° and 90° layers in $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ laminate. In $[0/+45/90/-45]_S$ laminate, the delamination occurred both $+45^\circ/90^\circ$ and $90^\circ/-45^\circ$ interlayers. As a result of the progressive delamination, 0° layers which possess the highest load carrying capability

could not sufficiently bear the load in $[0/\pm 45/90]_S$ and $[0/+45/90/-45]_S$ laminates. Consequently the fatigue strength of $[\pm 45/0/90]_S$ laminate was the highest in T800H/#3631 laminates. On the other hand, the progressive delamination was suppressed for all the stacking sequences in T800H/#3900 laminate because of the toughened resin phase at interlayer. In this case, the load carrying capability of 0° layer are supposed to be almost the same in all the laminates. As a result, the effect of the stacking sequence on the fatigue strength did not appear in T800H/#3900 laminate.

Figure 8. Relation between the maximum tensile stress and the number of fatigue cycles to failure for T800H/#3900 laminate.

Figure 9. Relation between the maximum tensile stress and the number of fatigue cycles to failure for T800H/#3631 laminate.

Fig.10 shows the ultrasonic C-scan inspection results for T800H/#3631 laminate after subjected to fatigue loading. In this laminate, the existence of delamination damage is observed at $-45^\circ/90^\circ$ interface near the free edges in the plane of the laminate in an early stage of fatigue, cycle ratio of 0.05. Such a free edge delamination develops rapidly with an increase of fatigue cycles and the ultrasonic C-scan inspection results at the cycle ratio of 0.13 revealed that the extremely remarkable delamination damage occurred, as shown in Fig.10(d). In about the middle stage of the fatigue life (cycle ratio of 0.51), only thin width of the specimen is adhered in the central area in the flat wise. The final failure was caused by the progression of such a free edge delamination in T800H/#3631 laminate. On the other hand, in T800H/#3900 laminate the free edge delamination damage was not remarkable and the dominant failure mode was multiple-splitting in 0° layer occurred when approaching to fatigue life, as shown in Fig.11. The final failure in T800H/#3900 laminate was mainly caused by such a splitting failure in 0° layer. These facts suggest that the existence of the particle in the matrix phase at interlayers is effective for suppressing the free edge delamination and this is probably main reason for the enhanced fatigue resistance in T800H/#3900 laminate.

Figs.12 and 13 show the fracture appearances of the specimens under compressive fatigue loading. Comparison of the fracture appearances clarified that damages at fiber/matrix interphase such as pull-out of the fibers and delamination was observed more in T800H/#3631 laminate than in T800H/#3900 laminate. Dominant failure mode in T800H/#3900 laminate was fiber breakage and thus final failure in this laminate tends to be localized as shown in Fig.12.

CONCLUSION

This study dealt with the effect of the particle dispersed interlayers on the fatigue strength of quasi-isotropic carbon/epoxy laminates. Two kinds of the laminates with and without the particle dispersed interlayers (T800H/#3900 and T800H/#3631 laminates) were adopted as the specimens. Tension, compression and fully reversed (tension-compression) fatigue tests were performed for these laminates. The particle dispersed interlayers affected greatly the tension fatigue strength, and the tension fatigue strength was remarkably improved by the incorporation of the particle dispersed layers. The particle dispersed interlayers suppressed the progression of the interlaminar

Figure 10. Ultrasonic C-scan inspection results for T800H/#3631 laminate subjected to tension fatigue loading (fatigue life : 39000 cycles).

Figure 11. Fracture progress of T800H/#3900 laminate subjected to tension fatigue loading (fatigue life : 23100 cycles)

delamination from the free edge. In addition, the compressive and the fully reversed fatigue strengths were also improved by the incorporation of the particle dispersed layers. Moreover the effect of the stacking sequence on the fatigue strength was discussed for both the laminates. In tension fatigue test, the progressive interlaminar delamination affects the fatigue strength of T800H/#3631 laminate, while the effect of the stacking sequence on the tensile fatigue strength did not appear in T800H/#3900 laminate because of the suppression of the delamination.

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Figure 12. Fracture appearance of T800H/#3900 laminate after compressive fatigue failure.

Figure 13. Fracture appearance of T800H/#3631 laminate after compressive fatigue failure.

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